

Welcome to “Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health”

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Dear Esteemed Readers,

Welcome to the inaugural issue of "*Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health*" (A.M.P.P.H.), a groundbreaking open-access academic journal. As we celebrate this significant milestone, it is an honor to present the "*International Network for the Advancement of Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health*" – a testament to our dedication to advancing knowledge and fostering collaboration in these crucial fields. This network has been established to synergize the expertise of specialists, clinicians, and academics in a global alliance championing interdisciplinary synergy and innovation in the critical domains of medicine, psychology, and public health to confront the intricate health challenges of our time.

As your Editor-in-chief, my professional journey, which began in 2016 with the creation of the "*Journal of Health and Social Sciences*" (J.H.S.S.), has been a path of continuous exploration and contribution to the study of social determinants of health and the disparities and challenges faced nationally and internationally in public health. This journey reached a significant milestone in 2019 with the journal's inclusion in the esteemed Scopus index (The CiteScore Tracker shows a score of 3,8 on 5 December 2023).

In 2020, this vision expanded with the establishment of the "*Italian Association of Psychology and Occupational Medicine*" (A.I.P.M.E.L.) and its affiliated publication, the "*Italian Journal of Psychology and Occupational Health*" (G.I.P.M.E.L.). A.I.P.M.E.L.'s foundational mission is to bridge the gap between occupational physicians and psychologists, addressing our interdisciplinary field's diverse and complex challenges.

At a recent conference in Fez, Morocco, organized by one of the Associate Editor of the J.H.S.S, Professor Hicham Khabbache, I presented a bold initiative designed to cultivate collaboration between our journal and a global network of psychologists, occupational health experts, and public health practitioners. This initiative is strategically positioned to tackle modern workplaces' unprecedented challenges, such as climate change, public health emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic, and various humanitarian crises.

Our focus is notably on the mental health consequences emerging from these global challenges. Therefore, A.M.P.P.H. is committed to exploring the dynamic interaction between technological progress, globalization, demographic shifts, and the associated risks and challenges these pose to workers and the broader population. Given the significant role mental disorders play in disability and global suicide rates, the need for effective workplace mental health strategies has never been more urgent.

This new international network underscores the critical importance of collaboration among occupational, environmental, and public health stakeholders. Our multidisciplinary approach, integrating insights from psychologists, social scientists, and medical experts, aims to deeply understand the impact of new global emergencies on psychological and physical health.

As we embark on this journey, "*Advances in Medicine, Psychology and Public Health*" will lead the discourse and action in addressing these vital issues. Our ambition extends beyond risk mitigation; we are committed to fostering an environment where individuals can thrive, be productive, and sustain mental health and physical well-being.

This inaugural issue is more than just a publication; it represents a call to action for collaborative, international scientific cooperation. We invite the academic community, practitioners, and policymakers to join hands in this essential endeavor. Together, we can face and shape the future, significantly influencing the lives of people and workers globally.

Thank you for your engagement, commitment, and active participation in this crucial dialogue.

Francesco Chirico, MD, Prof

Editor in Chief and Founder at *Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health*

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